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COMPOSITE COIL SPRINGS MADE BY 4D PRINTING METHOD

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents an application of the 4D printing of composites method. Composite coil springs having different types of lay up sequences are made and examined. The anisotropy of the structure makes it to change shape from springs with normal behavior to springs that exhibit lengthening, shortening and twist. The change in shape is characteristic of the 4D printing process. It is observed that springs made of anisotropic stacking sequence also exhibit change in the diameter and the fiber winding angle. These changing characteristics are due to the response to the application of heat. As such, these can be used as actuators in response to heat.

1. INTRODUCTION

3D printing is a popular technique for the additive manufacturing of complex structures. 4D printing method combines 3D printing of a flat stack of materials with the reconfiguration of the flat structure into a structure with complex geometry, upon some activation mechanism such as heat, light, or the absorption of liquid such as water [1, 2]. Both 3D printing and 4D printing usually use soft materials that may not possess high strength and high stiffness. This type of 4D printing is termed as “Regular 4D printing” in this work. 4D printing of composites (abbreviated as 4DPC) utilizes the concept of Regular 4D printing but 4DPC uses light weight, high strength, high stiffness composite materials that have been used to make engineering structures such as parts of aircrafts or automobiles. The method of manufacturing structures using 4DPC is via an Automated Fiber Placement (AFP) machine, where a robotic arm is used to deposit layers of the composite on a mandrel. The concept of 4DPC method was introduced in [3]. Composite leaf springs with high stiffness and strength have also been made using this method [4]. Composite layers were deposited onto a flat mold. Upon the activation of heat (curing of the composites), the flat layers become curved and this provides the shape for the leaf spring. The governing principle for the reconfiguration depends on the anisotropic nature of the composite lay up. By using the 4DPC, actuators can also be made using composite materials. The initial prepregs are wound helically on a simple cylindrical mandrel, to take the shape of coil springs. Depending on the lay up sequence, upon curing and cooling to room temperature, the length, diameter, and degree of twist of the final coil spring can be very different from the initial configuration. If these coil springs are subjected to heating from room temperature, their diameter, length and twist will significantly change. These changes can provide actuation mechanism.

2. EXPERIMENTAL WORK

The normal way to make composite coil springs is to wind strips of the composite (either prepregs, or dry tows of fiber to be wetted later) along a helical pattern. Fibers are usually unidirectional, as shown

in figure 1a. For the case where dry fibers are wound, resin is then applied on the fibers to wet the fibers. The uncured composite (either prepregs or wet fibers) is then heated to cure temperature. After curing the composite is cooled to room temperature to reach the final state of the product. The length, and diameter of the final coil spring are about the same as those of the initial configuration (compare figure 1a and figure 1c).

The material used was CYTEC Cycom 5320-1. Curing cycle: Heat ramp 1 hour to 180 °C, holding for 2.5 hours at 180 °C, then cool down. Bandwidth $b = 19.05$ mm (0.75 in). Mandrel diameter 28.6 mm. All samples have the same strip length L . These are then bagged and cured in either an autoclave or in an oven.

Depending on the lay up sequence in the composite stack, different behavior is observed. For example, consider the case where the spring thickness is made of 4 layers. For starter, simple lay up sequences consisting only of 0° and 90° layers are deposited on the mandrel. Four lay up sequences are considered in this work. These are $[0_4]$, $[0/90]_s$, $[0_2/90_2]$, or $[90_2/0_2]$. The prepreg layers are laid onto a cylindrical mandrel with the same pitch, bandwidth, and strip length, as shown in figures 1a. The configurations of the coil springs after curing are as follows:

Lay up sequence $[0_4]$:

The use of all unidirectional layers is similar to the manufacturing of normal composite coil springs. The final configuration of the coil spring (after curing and cooling) is shown in figure 1c. It can be seen that the pitch, gap, and total length of the final spring is very similar to the initial configuration.

Lay up sequence $[0/90]_s$:

This is a symmetric lay up sequence. The final configuration is shown in figure 1b. Again there is no significant difference between this configuration and the initial configuration.

Lay up sequence $[90_2/0_2]$:

The final configuration is shown in figure 1d. It can be seen that the total length of the coil spring is much shorter than the length in the initial configuration. The gaps between the bands are smaller than in the initial configuration.

Lay up sequence $[0_2/90_2]$:

The final configuration is shown in figure 1e. It can be seen that the total length of the coil spring is much longer than the initial configuration. The gaps between the bands are longer than those in the initial configuration. The width of the band seems to be shorter than that in the initial configuration.

Measurements were made on the dimensions of the coil spring in different configurations. The results are shown in Table 1. The following observations are made:

- The inside diameters D of all springs in the initial configuration are the same as the diameter of the mandrel. In the final configuration, springs with the unidirectional lay up and symmetric lay up maintain the same diameters. The diameter of the $[0_2/90_2]$ spring becomes larger while that of the $[90_2/0_2]$ spring becomes smaller.
- The total length of the springs, C , in the initial configuration, vary slightly due to the variation of the original composite strip that is used to make the composite spring. In the final configuration, the length of both the unidirectional spring and the symmetric lay up spring becomes slightly shorter (less than 5%). This is within the measurement error. This may also be due to the slight shrinkage of the resin due to curing. The $[0_2/90_2]$ spring becomes much longer (from 313.4 mm to 402.9 mm, or about 29%) while the $[90_2/0_2]$ spring becomes much shorter (from 310.4 mm to 269.3 mm, or 13%). Also the number of turns of the $[0_2/90_2]$ spring increases by one as compared to the initial configuration and to the configurations of other springs.

- The gap (axial distance between two bands) for the unidirectional and symmetric springs do not change much from the initial to the final configurations. For the $[0_2/90_2]$ spring, the gap increases from 16.2 mm to 26.5 mm, or 64%) while the gap for the $[90_2/0_2]$ spring decreases from 16.0 mm to 7.4 mm, or 54%).
- The width (axial direction of the composite band) show some slight change but this is within measurement error.
- The winding angle α (angle between the fiber direction and the longitudinal axis of the cylinder) for the unidirectional spring and the symmetric spring do not show significant change. For the $[0_2/90_2]$ spring, this angle decreases while that for the $[90_2/0_2]$ increases. Note that larger values of α would mean shorter total length of the spring. The extreme situation would be the case where $\alpha = 90^\circ$ (hoop wind) or slightly less than 90° which would result in the shortest spring length. This corresponds well in the values of the different parameters. In Table 1, row 4 for $[0_2/90_2]$ spring, the total length becomes longer and the angle α becomes less. Also, in row 5 for $[90_2/0_2]$ spring, the total length becomes shorter and the angle α becomes more.
- Some springs were observed to exhibit twisting. The twist angle is measured as follows. Before curing, a marker is used to draw a straight line parallel to the mandrel axis on the prepregs. To measure the total twist, the spring was positioned vertically on a paper sheet, and having its cross section's center coincident with the origin of the coordinate system drawn on the paper. The spring is rotated so that first marking on the spring (adjacent to the paper) is aligned with the "x" axis, and this is considered as the zero position. The last marking on the spring is "projected" on the paper using a right angle ruler. The angle measured between these two positions was considered the total angle of twist. The rate of twist is obtained by dividing the total angle by the number of turns from the first point to the last point. The unidirectional spring and the symmetric spring do not show any twist, while the $[0_2/90_2]$ and $[90_2/0_2]$ spring show significant amount of twist. Note that the twist for the $[0_2/90_2]$ spring has positive value while that for the $[90_2/0_2]$ spring has negative value.

Lay Up	D_1 (mm)	D_2 (mm)	C_1 (mm)	C_2 (mm)	g_1 (mm)	g_2 (mm)	W_1 (mm)	W_2 (mm)	$\alpha_1(o)$	$\alpha_2(o)$	Twist ($^\circ$)/rev
$[0_4]$	28.6	28.6	319.3	306.3	16.5	16.1	23.4	22.5	67.5	67.8	0
$[0/90]_s$	28.6	28.6	319.7	311.7	15.4	16.2	23.8	23.6	68.2	67.7	0
$[0_2/90_2]$	28.6	30.1	313.4	402.9	16.2	26.5	23.2	25.1	67.7	63.1	28.7
$[90_2/0_2]$	28.6	26.8	310.4	269.3	16.0	7.4	22.6	21.5	67.8	71.9	- 37

D_1, D_2 : Inside diameter of the spring before and after curing, and cooling.

C_1, C_2 : Length of the spring before and after curing and cooling.

g_1, g_2 : Gap between strips of the spring before and after curing and cooling.

W_1, W_2 : Width along the axial direction of springs before and after curing and cooling.

α_1, α_2 : Winding angle before and after curing and cooling.

Table 1: Dimensions of four composite springs- band width 190.5 mm (0.75 inch)-Pitch 38.1 mm (1.5 inch).

Figure 1: Composite springs 38.1 mm (1.5 in) pitch, bandwidth 19.05 mm (0.75 inch). (a) Before cure for all samples; After cure: (b) $[0/90]_s$, (c) $[0_4]$, (d) $[90_2/0_2]$, (e) $[0_2/90_2]$.

3. EXPLANATION FOR THE CHANGE IN CONFIGURATION

3.1 Spring parameters:

The wrapping of the tape around a cylindrical mandrel to make a coil spring is as shown in figure 2.

Figure 2: Wrapping tape around a cylindrical mandrel to make coil springs

The relations between the parameters are as follows:

Relation between pitch (p), fiber angle α and length of the fiber band (S) in one revolution:

$$p = S \cos \alpha \tag{1}$$

Relation between total strip length (L) and length of the spring (C) :

$$C = L \cos \alpha \quad (2)$$

$$C = np \quad L = nS \quad \text{where } n \text{ is the number of turns} \quad (3)$$

$$p = \frac{b}{\sin \alpha} + g \quad \text{where } b \text{ is the band width and } g \text{ is the gap in between strips} \quad (4)$$

$$\tan \alpha = \frac{\pi D}{p} \quad (5)$$

Combining equations (4) and (5), the gap can be shown to be:

$$g = \frac{\pi D}{\tan \alpha} - \frac{b}{\sin \alpha} = \frac{\pi D \cos \alpha - b}{\sin \alpha} \quad (6)$$

In summary, there are a total of 9 parameters: L, C, n, p, D, g, α , S, b.

$$\text{Let} \quad W = \frac{b}{\sin \alpha} \quad (7)$$

represent the width of the strip along the axial direction.

From the manufacturing point of view, at the beginning of the manufacturing process, L, D, b, and α should be known and fixed. The remaining parameters can be obtained from these four parameters as:

$$C = L \cos \alpha \quad (2)$$

$$n = \frac{L \sin \alpha}{\pi D} \quad (8)$$

$$p = \frac{\pi D}{\tan \alpha} \quad (9)$$

$$g = \frac{\pi D \cos \alpha - b}{\sin \alpha} \quad (6)$$

$$S = \frac{\pi D}{\sin \alpha} \quad (10)$$

The coil spring follows the form of a helix. The curvature of the coil spring is given as [5]:

$$K = \frac{R}{R^2 + (p/2\pi)^2} \quad (11)$$

Where R is the radius of the cylindrical mandrel.

The radius of curvature of the spring is then:

$$\rho = \frac{1}{K} = R + \frac{p^2}{R(4\pi^2)} \quad (12)$$

3.2 Effect of lay-up sequence on spring length:

When the composite prepregs are cured and cooled to room temperature, depending on the lay up sequence, the dimensions may change. This is particularly true for un-symmetric laminates such as

$[0_n/90_n]$ and $[90_n/0_n]$, or other types of un-symmetric laminates. In the notation, the angle that appears first represents the inner layer (in contact with the mandrel).

It was shown in [3] that laminates of lay up sequence $[90_n/0_n]$ will tend to bend inward. Due to the constraint of the surface of the mandrel, the composite tends to slip out as shown in figure 3. In figure 3a, considering an imaginary composite strip of length πR covering half the circumference of the mandrel. Upon cooling to room temperature after curing, the radius of the composite becomes $R' < R$. Because R' is less than R , the composite strip slips away from the mandrel. The overall effect of this motion results in the spring to have smaller diameter and shorter overall length. The wrapping angle is also affected. In figure 3b, the angle α becomes more. This corresponds to row 5 (and columns 10, 11) in Table 1.

Figure 3: Composite strip slipping out

On the other hand, for the case of the $[0_2/90_2]$ spring, upon cooling, the composite strip tends to bend away from the mandrel, thus increasing the radius of curvature. In order to compensate for this, the composite strip pushes toward the ends, thus making the fiber orientation more toward the axial direction (decreasing value of α). The end result is that the $[0_2/90_2]$ springs are longer than the initial length.

4. DISCUSSION

- It can be seen that by using un-symmetric laminates, one can produce composite coil springs that exhibit a significant degree of lengthening (or shortening) and twist. This was made only using lay up sequence consisting only of layers at 0° and 90° relative to axis of the springs. The degrees of freedom to affect these lengthening, shortening and twist can be increased with the use of layers at angle other than 0° and 90° with respect to the axis of the coil springs.
- The effects of the $[0_2/90_2]$ and $[90_2/0_2]$ lay up sequence on the change in configuration of the spring do not have the same intensity. For example, the lengthening for the $[0_2/90_2]$ spring is 89.5 mm (402.9-313.3) while the shortening for the $[90_2/0_2]$ spring is 41.1 mm (310.4 – 269.3). Another parameter is the degree of twist. The magnitude of the twist per revolution for the $[0_2/90_2]$ spring is 28.7° while that for the $[90_2/0_2]$ spring is -37° .
- By subjecting the springs to heat, the spring can be shortened or lengthened, or untwisted. These motions can provide actuation activities.

5. CONCLUSION

It was shown that by using un-symmetric lay up sequence for the laminate to make coil springs, using the concept of 4D printing of composites, one can produce coil springs that are lengthened, shortened, and/or twisted upon curing and cooling of the prepergs. From these deformed configurations, upon the application of heat, these structures can act as actuators.

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